

Estimation of tropane alkaloids using high performance thin layer chromatography

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A simple high performance thin layer chromatographic method for separation and estimation of tropane alkaloids hyoscyamine and hyoscyne is described. The method requires no special sample pretreatment and is suitable for rapid screening of plant material.

Some plants of the family Solanaceae are well known for the tropane alkaloids hyoscyamine and hyoscyne which are used in modern system of medicine for their mydriatic and anticholinergic actions¹. Paper chromatographic², spectrophotometric³ and high performance liquid chromatographic^{4,5} methods are used for the estimation of tropane alkaloids in the plant extracts, the latter being preferred due to its precision. The buffer solutions for mobile phase used in HPLC often create problems of corrosion and excessive wear of the pump and pump seal, leading to leaks in the system⁵. Buffer also damages the HPLC column making the technique costly for a routine analysis of large number of plant samples for crop improvement. Presently high performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC) is used as an alternative technique of HPLC for the quantitation of plant extracts because of its simplicity, accuracy, cost-effectiveness and rapidity⁶. HPTLC method for the analysis of alkaloids in Solanaceous plants has not yet been reported. A simple HPTLC method for the rapid analysis of major tropane alkaloids hyoscyamine and hyoscyne in *Duboisia myoporoides*, *Hyoscyamus niger*, *Datura metel* and *Hyoscyamus muticus* is described here. The assay combines the separation and determination of hyoscyamine and hyoscyne using a mobile phase of toluene-acetone-methanol-ammonia (20 : 20 : 6 : 1) on a silica gel 60F₂₅₄ HPTLC plate, followed by scanning at 530 nm (absorption-reflection mode).

Results and Discussion

By trying different compositions of the mobile phase, the desired resolution of hyoscyamine and hyoscyne with symmetrical and reproducible peaks was achieved by using toluene-acetone-methanol-ammonia (20 : 20 : 6 : 1) as mobile phase (Fig. 1). Peaks corresponding to hyoscyamine (A) and hyoscyne (B) were at R_f 0.35 and 0.57 respectively. The calibration curves of hyoscyamine and hyoscyne were linear in the range of 1–15 μ g and the linear regressions A (eqn : $Y = 1036.9 X - 245.47$) and B (eqn : $Y = 2094.9X - 414.64$) were 0.998 and 1.000 respectively. For the estimation of recovery rates, known amounts of stock

solutions of pure A and B were added to *D. myoporoides* plant extract and quantitative analysis was repeated thrice; the values were 98 and 96% respectively. Peak purity test was done on both A and B by comparing the spectra of these in standard and sample tracks.

Fig. 1. HPTLC separation of hyoscyamine (A) and hyoscyne (B) : (1) *H. niger*, (2) *H. muticus*, (3) standard, (4) *D. metel* and (5) *D. myoporoides*. Tracks at 530 nm visible absorption/reflection mode.

Chloroform, methanol, ethanol and acetone were used for the extraction of tropane alkaloids from the leaves of *D. myoporoides*. The results that are average of three readings showed that the respective contents of A and B were respectively 0.77 and 0.50% in the case of chloroform, 1.02 and 0.57% for methanol, 0.25 and 0.11% for acetone and 0.99 and 0.54% for ethanol. These results clearly showed that methanol was most suitable for maximum recovery of tropane alkaloids.

The method was applied to the leaf samples of certain accessions of *H. niger* (HN-1), *H. muticus* (HM-2), *D. metel* (DM-3) and *D. myoporoides* (DM-4). The contents of A and B were found to be 0.01, 0.01% in HN-1, 0.34, 0.03% in HM-2, 0.06, 0.16% in DM-3, and 1.02, 0.57% in DM-4 respectively. The considerable variation observed in the contents of the alkaloids demonstrated that the method would prove useful in the screening of variants in the breeding programmes of Solanaceous crops.

Experimental

The leaf material of *H. niger*, *H. muticus*, *D. metel* and *D. myoporoides* were obtained from the experimental farm of this institute at Lucknow and a voucher specimen of each has been deposited in the Gene Bank of this institute. Air-dried (35–50°) leaves of *H. niger* (2 g), *H. muticus* (1 g), *D. metel* (1 g) and *D. myoporoides* (0.5 g) were extracted separately in methanol for 12 h, filtered and evaporated. Each of the extracts thus obtained was defatted with hexane and redissolved in methanol (1 ml) for quantification.

Chromatography was performed on a preactivated (110°) silica gel HPTLC plate 60F₂₅₄ (E. Merck), 10 × 10 cm. Samples and standards (hyoscyamine and hyoscyne from Sigma) were applied to the plate as 6 mm wide bands with an automatic TLC applicator Linomate IV with N₂ flow (CAMAG, Switzerland), 2 cm from the bottom of the plate. The application parameters were identical for all the analyses performed.

The plates were developed in a CAMAG twin trough chamber which was presaturated with mobile phase toluene-acetone-methanol-ammonia (20 : 20 : 6 : 1) for 1 h and each plate was allowed to run for ~8 cm at room

temperature (25 ± 5°) and 50% relative humidity. The composition of mobile phase was optimized by using different mobile solvents of varying polarities. After development, the plate was withdrawn, dried and sprayed using Dragendorff reagent no. 11C⁷. Quantitative evaluation of the plates was performed in the absorption-reflection mode at 530 nm with a computerized CAMAG TLC scanner 3 using CATS4 software version 3.14; slit width 6 × 0.4 mm.

References

1. L. D. Kapoor, "CRC : Hand Book of Ayurvedic Medicinal Plants", CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1990.
2. T. Adzet and J. L. Masso, *Rev. R. Acad. Farm. Barcelona*, 1976, **13**, 35.
3. A. Bauer, *CLB Chem. Labor Betr.*, 1989, **40**, 57.
4. S. Paphassarang, J. Raynaud, R. P. Godean and A. M. Binsard, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1985, **319**, 412; T. Oshima, K. Saraga, Y. Tong, G. Zhang and Y. Chen, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1989, **37**, 2456; S. Auriola, A. Martinsen, K. M. Oksman-Caldentey and T. Naaranlah-ti, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1991, **562**, 734.
5. S. Mandal, A. A. Naqvi and R. S. Thakur, *Phytochem. Anal.*, 1991, **2**, 208.
6. "Practical Thin-Layer Chromatography (A Multidisciplinary Approach)", eds. B. Fried and J. Sherma, CRC Press, New York, p. 33; D. Heimlerand and A. Pieroni, *Chromatographia*, 1991, **31**, 247.
7. H. Wagner, S. Bladt and E. M. Zgainski, "Plant Drug Analysis", Translated : Th. A. Scott, Springer-Verlag, New York, 1984.